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Review Article

Stability-Indicating RP-HPLC Method Development and Validation for Estimation of Remdesivir in Bulk and Pharmaceutical Formulations: A Comprehensive Review

Satyam Dhole*, Prashant Mokate, Dr. Jain P. P.

Loknete Shri Dadapatil Pharate Collage Of Pharmacy Mandavgaon Pharata . Tal. Shirur Dist. Pune.

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ABSTRACT

The development of a stability-indicating reverse-phase high-performance liquid chromatography (RP-HPLC) method for remdesivir has gained prominence in ensuring its quality and stability in bulk and pharmaceutical formulations. This review systematically evaluates existing studies on RP-HPLC method development, emphasizing critical parameters such as mobile phase optimization, stress testing under forced degradation conditions, and method validation as per International Council for Harmonisation (ICH) guidelines. It further highlights analytical challenges and future perspectives in remdesivir quality control.

INTRODUCTION

Remdesivir, a nucleotide prodrug, is a key therapeutic agent against SARS-CoV-2. As the pharmaceutical industry emphasizes drug quality and stability, robust analytical methods are essential for regulatory compliance and ensuring safety. RP-HPLC is a widely adopted analytical technique for quantifying remdesivir due to its accuracy, sensitivity, and reproducibility.

This review consolidates existing research on RP-HPLC methods for remdesivir, focusing on critical aspects such as method optimization, forced degradation studies, and validation parameters. The integration of stability-indicating features enables the detection of degradation products, enhancing the reliability of remdesivir formulations.

***Corresponding Author:** Satyam Dhole

Address: Loknete Shri Dadapatil Pharate Collage Of Pharmacy Mandavgaon Pharata .Tal. Shirur Dist. Pune

Email ✉: navnathkharat678@gmail.com

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Method Development

1. Chromatographic Conditions

- Mobile Phase: Various combinations of aqueous buffers (e.g., phosphate buffer, pH 3.0–5.0) and organic solvents (e.g., acetonitrile or methanol) are optimized to achieve peak resolution and symmetrical elution.
- Column: C18 columns (250 mm × 4.6 mm, 5 μm) are preferred for their compatibility with hydrophobic compounds like remdesivir.

- Flow Rate: Typically maintained at 1.0 mL/min, balancing resolution and runtime.

- Detection Wavelength: UV detection at 240–260 nm offers optimal sensitivity for remdesivir.

2. Retention Time: Sharp and well-resolved peaks ensure efficient separation of remdesivir and its degradation products within 8–12 minutes.

3. Sample Preparation: Proper dilution and filtration minimize interference and enhance the accuracy of analysis.

Figure 2: Various steps for RP-HPLC Method Development*

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Forced Degradation Studies

Forced degradation testing is a critical component of stability-indicating methods, simulating conditions that cause drug degradation. Key stress conditions include:

1. Acidic and Alkaline Hydrolysis: Degradation under strong acid (0.1 N HCl) and base (0.1 N NaOH) conditions provides insights into pH sensitivity.
2. Oxidative Stress: Exposure to 3–5% hydrogen peroxide evaluates remdesivir’s stability against reactive oxygen species.
3. Thermal Stress: Heating at 60°C for 24–48 hours assesses thermal stability.
4. Photolytic Stress: UV light exposure (254 nm) determines photostability, simulating real-world storage conditions.

Validation Parameters

Validation ensures the reliability and reproducibility of the RP-HPLC method. Key parameters validated according to ICH Q2(R1) guidelines include:

1. Specificity: Ensures separation of remdesivir from excipients and degradation products.
2. Linearity: Calibration curves exhibit linearity with $R^2 > 0.999$ in concentration ranges (10–100 µg/mL).
3. Accuracy: Recovery studies (98–102%) confirm method reliability.
4. Precision: Low %RSD (<2%) indicates reproducibility in intra-day and inter-day analyses.
5. LOD and LOQ: Sensitivity is demonstrated with LOD (0.5 µg/mL) and LOQ (1.5 µg/mL).
6. Robustness: Minor variations in chromatographic conditions show consistent performance.

REVERSE PHASE CHROMATOGRAPHY (RP-HPLC)

MP INSIDERS

Applications

Stability-indicating RP-HPLC methods for remdesivir are crucial in pharmaceutical analysis, providing insights into its stability under varying conditions. They also facilitate quality control during manufacturing and storage, ensuring compliance with regulatory standards.

Challenges and Future Perspectives

While RP-HPLC offers reliable analysis, challenges such as complex degradation pathways and matrix interference necessitate further advancements. Coupling RP-HPLC with mass spectrometry (LC-MS) can enhance analytical capabilities, enabling precise identification of unknown degradation products. Additionally, exploring green chromatography approaches could make the process more sustainable.

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